

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Establishing a Flow Scheme to Discover Novel PLC γ 2 Chemical Probes

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Introduction:

Late-onset Alzheimer's disease (LOAD) is a devastating neurodegenerative disorder that affects millions worldwide. Genome-wide association studies (GWAS), whole-genome sequencing, and gene-expression network analyses have unveiled protective and risk genes involved in microglial function and neuroinflammation.¹ The 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLCG2) gene encodes the 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2) enzyme known to be associated with LOAD.^{2,3,4} PLC γ 2 plays a crucial role in converting phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate [PI(4,5)P₂] into 1D-myo-inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP₃) and diacylglycerol (DAG) (**Figure 1A**).

Notably, PLC γ 2 is predominantly expressed in immune cells and microglia, with much lower expression in other brain cells, such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.⁵ Recently, a rare coding variant of PLC γ 2, known as PLC γ 2^{P522R}, has been found to provide a protective effect in Alzheimer's patients, leading to a slower rate of cognitive decline.¹ While the precise mechanisms underlying the observed protective effect of PLC γ 2^{P522R}, a functional hypermorph,⁵ remains incompletely understood, the lower expression⁶ and activity of the risk variant PLC γ 2^{M28L} suggests the protective effect is linked to the increased activity of PLC γ 2^{P522R}.

Figure 1. A: The primary function of PLC γ 2 is the cleavage of PI(4,5)P₂ into diacylglycerol (DAG) and inositol triphosphate. **B and C:** Depictions of PLC γ 2 domains based on PDB 6PBC of PLC γ 1.

Figure 2. Proposed mechanism of PLC γ enzymes transitioning from the autoinhibited to the active state. (Created in BioRender).

The complex multidomain protein PLC γ 2 adopts an autoinhibited state where the regulatory domains obstruct its binding to PIP₂ at the cell membrane surface (**Figure 1**). The exact mechanism of the conversion to the active state is not fully understood, but much can be inferred based on the known roles of spleen tyrosine kinase (SYK), B cell linker (BLNK), and Bruton's agammaglobulinemia tyrosine kinase (BTK) in B-cells^{7,8,9,10} and hydrogen–deuterium exchange (HDX) studies of 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-1 (PLC γ 1)¹²

In the triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) pathway, SYK is activated and BLNK is phosphorylated, forming an activation complex comprising these two enzymes and PLC γ 2 (**Figure 2**). This complex might initiate the detachment of PLC γ 2's regulatory domain from its catalytic site, priming the enzyme for full activation. Subsequent phosphorylation by SYK and BTK, with Tyr759 being the most crucial, induces a conformational change, disrupting interactions with the catalytic core and exposing membrane-binding surfaces and the active site. Molecular dynamics simulations revealed that the P522R protective variant significantly alters the position, structure, and flexibility of the nSH2 domain,¹³ suggesting the possibility of identifying molecules that bind at the SH2 domain interface, activate PLC γ 2, and break interactions with the catalytic core domains. Thus, identifying molecules that bind at the SH2 domain interface and break interactions with the catalytic core domains is a potential strategy for activating PLC γ 2.

We recently published¹⁶ data showing the lack of PLC γ 2 engagement between the reported activator m-3M3FBS¹⁷ with the protein. The activation ability of this compound has been controversial,^{18,19} and our data confirms this skepticism. To identify potential PLC γ 2 activators, approximately 48,000 compounds were screened using affinity selection mass spectrometry (ASMS).²⁰ Solutions of PLC γ 1 and PLC γ 2 were incubated with pools of eight compounds per well for 30 minutes to account for any slow on rates. Subsequently, a portion of these mixtures was transferred to biochip arrays functionalized with a Tris-Ni-NTA-presenting self-assembled monolayer to immobilize the His-tagged proteins. The arrays were incubated for 90 min in a humidified chamber, mitigating evaporation-related issues. The arrays were subjected to a rapid <3 second gentle wash step with deionized ultra-filtered water and dried with compressed air. ASMS was performed using the reflector positive mode on an AB Sciex TOF-TOF 5800 System (AB Sciex, Framingham, MA). Compounds showing sufficient signal compared to the background were retested to confirm their affinity using the same method but in a single compound per well format. The best compounds were then evaluated in dose response (0.195–100 μ M). **Table 1** shows compounds identified by this method along with physical property information.

Compound	MW (g/mol)	cLogP ⁱ	cLogD ⁱⁱ	tPSA ⁱⁱⁱ	H-bond donors	H-bond acceptors	Lipinski violations ^{iv}	CNS MPO score ^v	BBB Score ^{vi}
1	355.34	3.8	3.7	64.1	1	5	0	4.6	3.9
2	347.44	4.3	2.7	46.9	1	4	0	4.8	3.9
3	282.34	3.4	3.4	54.3	0	6	0	5.1	4.4
4	352.42	4.3	4.3	60.4	1	5	0	4.2	3.9
5	343.77	4.1	3.5	87.3	2	6	0	4.2	3.0
6	391.49	5.0	4.0	92.5	1	7	1	3.5	3.3
7	343.82	2.8	2.8	55.6	0	6	0	5.6	4.4
8	383.40	4.4	4.3	56.2	1	5	0	3.9	4.0
9	374.42	5.6	5.3	41.9	0	4	1	3.9	4.8
10	441.58	5.8	4.9	79.4	1	6	1	3.3	3.9
11	359.47	4.0	4.0	56.3	0	4	0	4.5	4.8
12	404.92	4.4	3.5	78.1	2	6	0	3.7	3.2

Table 1. Physical properties of preliminary screening hits. ⁱChemAxon calculated partition coefficient of the ratio of the concentration of the compound in octanol to its concentration in water. ⁱⁱChemAxon calculated octanol-water distribution coefficient (from pKa and cLogP); ⁱⁱⁱTopological polar surface area (Å²) based on the method of Ertl et al.;¹¹ ^{iv}See Lipinski et al.;¹⁴ ^vCentral Nervous System Multiparameter Optimization score based on the method of Wager et al.;¹⁵ ^{vi}Blood Brain Barrier penetration predictive score.²¹

The target engagement of these preliminary hits was evaluated in a cellular environment, via a cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA).²² HEK293t cells were stably transfected with PLCG2-HiBit to enable protein expression in a physiologically relevant cellular context. The thermal stability of this HiBit-labeled protein in intact cells was measured in the following two formats. In the initial screen, cells were treated in 96-well plates with compounds at a single concentration (100 μM) at 37 °C for 60 min and then exposed to a 3-min isothermal heating step at 45.9 °C (experimentally determined T_m of PLCG2-HiBit). Luminescence detection was then conducted with the Nano-Glo HiBit Lytic detection kit (Promega, Cat. N3040).²³ Compound treatment was performed in triplicate, and raw signals were normalized to the mean of the controls (in the same plate) as percentage of control. When the difference in compound-treated

cells > control mean + 3SD, the compound was considered positive and selected for further testing with dose-response CETSA. In the dose-response CETSA, cells were treated with decreasing concentrations from 100 μ M with 1:3 serial dilutions to generate an 8-point curve. An AC₅₀ was calculated with the percentage of control data using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model, and the percent luminescence remaining at the highest concentration is also reported for the compounds when the difference from the DMSO control was greater than 3x the standard deviation (SD). Otherwise, an AC₅₀ was not calculated. Compounds with promising results were further tested with HiBit only to ensure the observed response was not due to test compounds interacting directly with the HiBit itself. Only compound **7** showed a significant destabilization effect on PLC γ 2 (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. A: Cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA) results taken at 100 μ M. **B:** Representative CETSA dose response curves from 0.05-100 μ M. ● HiBit-PLC γ 2, ▲ HiBit only.

Figure 4. A: Progress curves for the hydrolysis of XY-69 by PLC γ 2 in the presence and absence of compound **7**. **B:** Phagocytosis in HMC3 cells. ● Cell count, ■ Nuclear intensity, ▲ Phagocytosis.

After confirming target engagement of **7** to PLC γ 2, attention was turned to measuring the impact on PLC γ 2 activity both in a biochemical and cellular context. Sondek and coworkers have described a liposomal assay capable of measuring PLC γ 1 activity mimicking enzymatic action at the cell membrane where the natural ligand is located.²⁴ This assay was modified for PLC γ 2 at the Purdue Institute for Drug Discovery.²⁵ Liposomes containing XY-69 (purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids, cat. # 850168) were generated using phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) and 1-stearoyl-2-arachidonoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylethanolamine (lipidPE). The PLC γ 2 enzyme was exposed to this solution and, after treatment with the compounds of interest, the fluorescence intensity (ex: 485 nm; em: 520 nm) was recorded every 2 min for 120 min. **7** caused an increase in phospholytic activity, albeit only at the highest concentration measured (**Figure 4 A**).

PLC γ 2 activity has been shown to induce phagocytosis in microglia as part of the TREM2 pathway.²⁶ **7** was evaluated for phagocytotic activity as well as cell health in a single assay. HMC3 cells (immortalized human microglia, obtained from ATCC, CRL-3304) were used to provide adequate throughput. Cells were cultured in Corning Falcon 384-well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) GlutaMax media (Thermo Fisher) containing 10% FBS and 1% pen/strep in a 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator (600 cells/45 μ l/well (HMC3 cells)). The cells were then treated with 10x serially diluted compounds (60 μ M–3 nM) for 48 hrs at 37°C and seeded with pHrodo-myelin (20 hrs total) 24 hrs after compound treatment initiation; 1 mg/ml (protein equivalent) pHrodo-myelin stocks were stored at -20°C or -80°C, thawed, diluted with culture media to produce a 10x seeding solution (50 μ g/ml) and added to the 384-well plate (5 μ l/well). Nuclear staining solution (1 μ l of 10 mg/ml Hoechst-33342 per 1 ml culture media; 20 μ l/well) was added to a final concentration of 2.5 μ g/ml, and the plates were incubated for 30 min at 37°C and then scanned with an ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system (10x objective lens, 4 fields/well collected). The mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, total cell counts per well, and mean average nuclear intensity per cell for cell health were measured. Cellular potencies for each endpoint (EC₅₀ for phagocytosis, IC₅₀ for cell count) were calculated using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model. The ideal PLC γ 2 activator would show an increase in phagocytosis (red) without a sharp decrease in the cell count (blue), with the nuclear intensity (black) remaining unchanged. We were pleased to see **7** caused an increase in phagocytosis with an EC₅₀ of 3.51 μ M (**Figure 4 B**). The accompanying decrease in the cell count does not match the typical readout of cytotoxic test compounds. Such compounds typically result in a sharp decline of the cell count down to zero with a significant change to the nuclear intensity. In the case of **7** the decrease is gradual and levels off around 50% with virtually no change in the nuclear intensity. Thus **7** is not believed to be cytotoxic leading to cell death. Further studies are underway to better understand this phenomenon.

The physicochemical and ADME properties of **7** were determined using the following assays: microsomal stability intrinsic clearance (Cl_{int}) in mouse liver microsomal solution, MDCK permeability (Papp), protein binding (f_u) in mouse plasma and brain, and kinetic solubility in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The data in **Table 2** coupled with the CNS MPO and BBB scores in **Table 1** indicate that **7** possesses characteristics consistent with a hit compound suitable for a CNS drug discovery program.

Cl_{int} ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$) ⁱ 85.0 Papp ($\times 10^{-6}$ cm/s) ⁱⁱ 66.2 $f_{u, \text{plasma}}$ ⁱⁱⁱ 0.017 $f_{u, \text{brain}}$ ^{iv} 0.019 Kinetic solubility (μM) ^v 61-80	We established a flow scheme consisting of MALDI-ASMS, CETSA, and phagocytosis/cell health assays as successful method and have discovered the first activator of PLC γ 2. Starting from a pool of ~48,000 compounds, 7 was identified as showing target engagement, biochemical activation, an expected phenotypic response, and desirable ADME properties. Future work including structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies improve potency and solubility to produce lead compounds suitable for evaluation of PLC γ 2 activation as a strategy for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.
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Table 2. Measured physicochemical and ADME properties of **7**. ⁱIntrinsic clearance in mouse liver microsomes. ⁱⁱMDCK permeability assay as an estimate of intestinal absorption. ⁱⁱⁱMouse plasma fraction unbound. ^{iv}Mouse brain fraction unbound. ^vKinetic solubility in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer.

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